

virescens (see table). The early-planted crops were significantly more severely infected with RTV, resulting in lower grain yield, than late planting. Severe RTV infection in the early samba crop was due to overlapping of younger plants with the sornavari season (May planting) older crop that had high RTV incidence and vector population. When the vector population declined later, RTV incidence also was reduced. We concluded that the spread of RTV was mainly influenced by the vector population. □

Effect of planting time and field population of green leafhopper on RTV incidence.^a Tirur, India, 1984.

Planting date	RTV incidence ^b (%)	Grain yield (t/ha)	GLH in light trap (no./mo)
10 Aug	68.6 g	0.97 e	Jul : 181,196
20 Aug	60.6 f	1.77 d	Aug : 30,343
30 Aug	19.6 e	2.60 c	Sep : 2,407
10 Sep	8.1 d	2.43 c	Oct : 906
20 Sep	1.9 c	4.27 a	Nov : 1,278
30 Sep	2.1 c	3.60 b	
10 Oct	1.0 b	2.57 c	
20 Oct	1.2 bc	2.57 c	
30 Oct	0.2 a	2.47 c	
CD (P = 0.05)	1.95	0.36	

^a Means in a column followed by a common letter are not statistically significant at the 5% level.
^b Mean of 3 replications.

A new annelidan pest of rice in Nepal

S. B. Pradhan, Entomology Division, Khumaltar, Nepal

A new pest of rice, tentatively named "Sano Gadeula" (small earthworm), was recorded in farmers' fields during the 1980 crop in the plains and hills of Nepal (see figure). The pest was identified in Japan as *Limnodrilus* sp., phylum Annelida and class Oligochaeta.

Fields infested with this pest

resemble Zn-deficient plots. Leaves of infested plants turn yellow or brown and the plant is stunted. Severely infested plants die.

Closer observation revealed newly hatched worms in the basal part of the plant tissue. Mature worms usually were found in clusters in the roots and the underground basal parts of the plant.

Feeding habits of the worm and plant injury are under study. The worm can survive in fresh water for several days, even without soil, but when exposed without water or soil,

Limnodrilus sp., a new pest of rice found in Nepal.

dies within a minute because of dehydration. □

Caseworm (CW) preference for vegetative stage rice

N. Chantaraprapha, Entomology and Zoology Division, Department of Agriculture, Bangkok, Thailand; and J.A. Litsinger, Entomology Department, IIRRI

CW *Nymphula depunctalis* moths oviposit on the undersides of leaves floating in water. In a no-choice test, most eggs were laid on floating leaves, a few on erect leaves, and some on leaves bent in water (Table 1).

In 13 plots exhibiting all plant growth stages, we randomly sampled 20 hills per growth stage and recorded the number of leaves touching the water. Only vegetative stage rice had significant numbers of leaves in contact with water.

A free-choice test measured

oviposition by seedling age. Potted plants of different ages were immersed in a drum filled with water set so that leaves of each age were at the same distance above the water surface. The number of eggs laid on seedlings 1, 2,

3, 4, and 5 wk after sowing did not differ.

A preference to oviposit on leaves 2, 4, 6, and 8 mm wide was tested. Excised 4-wk-old floating leaves were randomly pinned to submerged stakes

Table 1. Ovipositional preference of *N. depunctalis* on IR36 rice at different plant ages.^a IIRRI greenhouse, 1983-84.

Plant age ^b (WT)	Oviposition site ^c (no. eggs/10 females per 3 d)		
	Excised floating leaves	Leaves bent in water	Erect leaves
2	123 b	157 a	85 a
4	378 a	189 a	157 a
6	278 ab	153 a	37 b
8	201 ab	179 a	35 b
10	109 b	90 a	31 b
Mean	218	153	69

^a Av of 6 replications, 10 females and males per replication. Potted plants and excised leaves were placed in mesh-covered 44-gallon gasoline drum cages 3/4 full of water. Floating and bent leaves were pinned to submerged stakes. ^b Transplanted 3 wk after germination. WT = wk after transplanting. ^c In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different by DMRT at the 5% level.

and 5 pairs of moths released. After 3 d, the number of eggs laid on leaves of different widths did not differ.

CW reared on potted 2- to 6-wk-old rice had shorter larval development period and higher larval weight, and growth index, survivorship, and fertility (Table 2).

We conclude that suitable oviposition sites occur only during the vegetative stage. CW on older rice have low survival and slow development. □

Table 2. Effect of rice plant age on growth and development of *N. depunctalis*.^a IRRI greenhouse, 1983-84.

Plant age ^b (WT)	Larval wt (mg)	Larval developmental period (d)	Growth index ^c	Survivorship from larva to adulthood (d)	Fertility (no. of eggs/female)
2	5.76 b	18 ab	4.7 ab	65 a	111 a
4	7.07 a	15 a	5.6 a	69 a	117 a
6	8.24 a	17 a	4.3 b	63 a	108 a
8	4.47 c	21 c	2.7 c	37 b	67 b
10	3.89 d	20 bc	2.1 c	36 b	74 b

^a Av of 6 replications of 25 insects each replication. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different by DMRT at the 5% level. ^b Transplanted 3 wk after germination.

^c Growth index = pupation (%) / larval developmental period (d).

Bioefficacy of seven insecticides against leaffolder *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* Guenée in India

R.M. Bhagat, Himachal Pradesh Agricultural University (HPAU) Malan, 176047 Himachal Pradesh, India

A replicated trial was laid out in a randomized complete block design in 1984 kharif at the HPAU Rice Research Station to evaluate seven insecticides: quinalphos, carbofuran, monocrotophos, benfuracarb, bromophos-ethyl, ethoprop, and UC54229. Insecticides were applied as needed at 26 and 38 d after transplanting (DT). Damage was

assessed at 50 DT.

All insecticides were superior to the untreated control (see table).

UC54229, quinalphos, and monocrotophos are promising for checking leaffolder damage. □

Effect of 7 insecticides on leaffolder damage and yield of cultivar Himalaya 1 at Malan, H. P., India, 1984.^a

Insecticide	Rate (kg ai/ha)	Leaffolder damage (%)	Damage decrease (%)	Grain yield (t/ha) ^a	Yield increase (%)
Quinalphos 3G	1.5	1.5 d	89.3	3.9 a	61.6
Carbofuran 3G	1.0	2.3 cd	83.6	3.4 b	40.6
Monocrotophos 40EC	0.5	1.9 cd	86.5	3.1 bc	29.0
Benfuracarb 3G	1.5	2.7 c	80.8	3.0 cd	25.5
Bromophos-ethyl 5G	1.5	2.4 c	82.9	2.9 cd	23.2
Ethoprop 10G	1.5	3.7 b	73.7	2.7 de	13.9
UC 54229 99SP	0.75	1.3 d	90.7	2.7 de	11.6
Untreated control	—	14.1 a	—	2.4 e	—

^a In a column, figures followed by the same letter are not significantly different from each other.

Nuclear polyhedrosis virus for controlling the ear-cutting caterpillar

D. T. Ho, Solrice, G.P.O. Box 5, Honiara, Solomon Islands

The ear-cutting caterpillar *Mythimna separata* (Walker) damages rice in the Solomon Islands. The mature caterpillar cuts the panicles of ripening rice. Early infestations are minor but a late infestation with old larvae causes serious damage and heavy yield loss. The immature stage consists of six larval stadia; larvae of the last two instars are ravenous feeders. In the field, a viral disease occasionally caused high mortality of young larvae.

M. separata's nuclear polyhedrosis virus (*Ms* NPV) was first studied in the

early 1970s in India, but the virus has not been formulated and used commercially. *Authographa californica*'s NPV (*A.cal* NPV) was first isolated in the early 1960s from a diseased larva in a California alfalfa field. *A.cal* NPV has a large host spectrum including 9 families (Lepidoptera), 29 genera, and 35 species of insect pests. This has aroused worldwide interest in its potential as a broad-spectrum microbial control agent.

We used *Ms*NPV and *A.cal* NPV from the Institute of Virology (IOV), Oxford, U.K., to test insects collected from the Solomons. The bioassay was conducted at the IOV in Oct 1985.

Larvae of *M. separata* were reared on an artificial diet with basic elements

from brewer yeast and red kidney bean extracts. Thirty 2d-instar larvae were used for each of three replications per treatment. With a vacuum suction device, 10 mg of the diet was put in a compartment of a transparent multicompartment plate. One larva was placed in each of the other compartments. Then the viral suspension was released onto the diet at 1 µl/larva. Untreated control insects were fed with the same diet and water. At 3 d after treatment (DAT), all insects were transferred into 4-cm-diam butter cups filled to 1.5 cm depth with the diet, at 1 larva/cup.

Mortality was recorded at 7 and 14 DAT. The midgut of dead larvae was smeared on slides and stained with naphthalene black for diagnosis under